

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE ACTIVITIES OF JUSTICE BODIES AND INSTITUTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15517753>

In the process of building a legal democratic state and a just civil society, a crucial role is assigned to justice bodies and institutions. Their primary aim is to implement a unified state legal policy, which includes organizing high-quality lawmaking activities, establishing consistent and uniform law enforcement practices, ensuring effective protection of human rights and freedoms, as well as introducing a comprehensive system for enhancing the legal culture of the population.

One of the priority areas of their activity is transforming justice bodies into a professional service that ensures the implementation of a unified state legal policy. This policy is aimed at putting into practice the conceptual idea that “adopting fair laws and instilling a spirit of respect for the law in society is the key to building a democratic state governed by the rule of law” [1].

In particular, the legal basis for the activities of justice bodies is regulated by a number of normative legal acts. These activities include coordinating, controlling, and providing methodological support for the legal services of state bodies and organizations, as well as economic management bodies. Additionally, these acts govern the justice bodies’ participation in appointing and dismissing legal service employees, improving their qualifications, conducting attestations, and addressing other related matters.

In accordance with these regulatory legal documents, the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan performs the following functions in the sphere of coordinating, controlling, and providing methodological support for the activities of legal services in state bodies and organizations:

- studies the activities of legal services and the status of legal work carried out by them;
- takes measures to eliminate identified violations of legislative requirements regulating the activities of legal services, as well as to hold responsible persons accountable in accordance with the law;
- participates in the appointment and dismissal of legal services personnel;

- provides guidance to legal services on legal matters;
- organizes professional development for legal services staff;
- establishes the procedure for certifying legal services personnel and issues certification certificates;
- maintains records of legal services employees;
- determines the procedure for creating and maintaining the legal services database, as well as the forms and deadlines for submitting information for inclusion in the database;
- establishes the procedure for coordinating with justice authorities on the appointment and dismissal of legal service employees;
- determines the procedure for legal service employees to undergo internships in justice bodies;
- organizes internships for individuals appointed to legal service positions for the first time;
- provides methodological support for the activities of legal services;
- develops and approves minimum requirements for the material and technical equipment of workplaces for legal service employees.

Furthermore, by Resolution No. 250 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 1, 2017, "On measures to implement the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2733 dated January 19, 2017 "On measures for fundamental improvement of legal service activities", the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan is also entrusted with the following tasks:

- a) ensuring systematic and comprehensive monitoring and analysis of compliance with the requirements of legislation regulating the activities of legal services by the legal departments of state bodies and organizations;
- b) when necessary, submitting proposals aimed at further improving the legislation on legal services through established procedures;
- c) taking measures to eliminate, in accordance with established procedures, instances where employees of legal services and other officials violate the requirements of legislation regulating the activities of legal services.

The Regulation on the Ministry of Justice stipulates that the Ministry has the following rights to carry out its assigned tasks and functions:

- to inspect the state of rule-making activities, legal work, operations of legal services, publication of normative legal acts, and their dissemination to interested parties in state bodies and organizations;

- to submit mandatory recommendations on preventing violations identified in the activities of legal services of state bodies and organizations, and eliminating the causes and conditions contributing to their occurrence;

- to submit proposals to the relevant state bodies on holding responsible officials accountable in cases where violations of legislation in the sphere of legal services activities are detected and when the lawful requirements of justice bodies are not fulfilled;

- to terminate the validity of the certificate of attestation of a legal service employee.

It also stipulates that the ministry may have other rights in accordance with the legislation. For example, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 13, 2018 No. PF-5415 "On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the Activities of Justice Bodies and Institutions in the Implementation of State Legal Policy" grants the Ministry of Justice the right to send employees of the legal services of state bodies and organizations to leading educational institutions and other organizations of developed countries for training and advanced training in the field of providing legal assistance at the expense of extra-budgetary funds, including in international arbitration and litigation. Control over the implementation of the "Rules for Maintaining Systematized Records of Legislation in State Administration Bodies and Local Government Bodies" is carried out by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its territorial administrations in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 13, 2018 No. PQ-3666.

The main tasks of the newly created justice departments of districts (cities) are defined, in particular, monitoring the state of legal work in the district (city) structures of state bodies and organizations, as well as coordination, control and methodological support of the activities of their legal services, which will serve to increase the effectiveness of work in this area at the district and city levels [2].

Today, the interdepartmental management function of the legal service of the Ministry of Justice is carried out by the Department for Coordination of the Activities of Legal Services of the Ministry, and in the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the departments of justice of the regions and the city of Tashkent - by the Departments of Legal Expertise and Coordination of the Activities of Legal Services.

In accordance with the Regulation, approved by Order No. 134 of the Minister of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 4, 2018, the main

tasks and areas of activity of the Department for Coordination of the Activities of Legal Services are:

a) coordination and development of legal work in state bodies and organizations, as well as development of recommendations for its improvement;

b) control over the fulfillment by employees and officials of legal services of the requirements of the legislation regulating the activities of legal services in state bodies and organizations;

c) coordination, methodological guidance and control of the activities of local government bodies in the field of rule-making.

In order to perform the tasks and functions assigned to it, the local Department has the right, in particular [3]:

- to request, demand, and receive from state bodies and organizations, as well as their officials, documents, statistical and other data, analytical materials, conclusions, and other information on issues within their competence;

- submit proposals on improving legislation for consideration by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other state bodies in the prescribed manner;

- to receive from ministries, state committees, departments, educational, scientific institutions and other organizations conclusions on draft laws and other regulatory legal acts and, in agreement with the heads of the specified bodies and organizations, to create commissions (working groups) for the preparation of these drafts;

- development and submission to the management of proposals for improving the legal services sector of state bodies and organizations;

- to inspect the state of legal work in state bodies and organizations, as well as the activities of their legal services, to demand from them the submission of information on the work performed, to submit to the heads of these bodies and organizations submissions on the elimination of identified shortcomings, mandatory for execution within the established timeframe, to apply to higher authorities or to the court with a question of bringing officials to responsibility for violations of legislation or compensation for material damage caused to the state or organization through their fault;

- submit to local government bodies representations on the elimination of violations identified in the process of monitoring the rule-making activities of these bodies, on the need to adopt normative legal acts, indicating the timeframe for their development, on the need for an official interpretation of the normative legal acts adopted by them, on the cancellation of normative legal acts that do

not comply with the legislation, or on bringing them into compliance with the legislation;

- submit to the attestation commission a proposal to terminate the validity of the certificate of certification of a legal service employee in accordance with the legislation;

- submitting proposals to the attestation commission on the deprivation or reduction of the class rank of employees of the legal service;

The foregoing indicates that the powers of justice bodies in the field of coordination, control, and methodological support of the activities of legal services of state bodies and organizations are clearly defined by law, and they carry out their activities within the framework of these powers [4].

In our opinion, in order to further improve the activities of justice bodies and institutions, it is advisable to pay attention to the following aspects:

firstly, it is necessary to further strengthen the influence of artificial intelligence on digitalization processes at the activities of justice bodies and institutions;

secondly, it's recommended to further improve the social protection and financial support of employees working in the justice bodies of the regions;

thirdly, it's advisable to centralize the system of preparing, training, retraining, and advanced training of legal personnel and coordinate scientific legal research activity in the justice system based on a unified approach;

and finally, it is proposed to fully digitize the system of archival and executive affairs and reduce the human factor in this area.

References:

1. Adliya organlari tomonidan boshqa tashkilotlarda nazorat tadbirlarini amalga oshirish va ta'sir choralarini (namunalar) qo'llash tartibini ishlab chiqish asoslari: O'quv qo'llanma / tuzuvchilar: S.Maripova, V.Usmonov. – T.: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Adliya vazirligi qoshidagi Yuristlar malakasini oshirish markazi, 2022. - 78 b.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 17-martdagi PF-89-son "Fuqarolarning huquq va erkinliklarini ta'minlash hamda huquqiy xizmat ko'rsatishda adliya organlari va muassasalari faoliyati samaradorligini yanada oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi Farmoni. Elektron resurs: <https://lex.uz/docs/5914998> // murojaat sanasi: 23-may 2025-yil.
3. Adliya organlari: vazifalari, faoliyatining asosiy yo'nalishlari (Rossiya Federatsiyasi misolida) // <https://uz.workingrede.com/10722077-justice-bodies-tasks-main-directions-of-activity>.

4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi adliya vazirining 2021-yil 17-iyundagi 187-um-son "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Adliya vazirligining Sifat menejmenti tizimi sohasidagi siyosatini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi buyrug'i.